

**PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF ALKALI-MODIFIED NATURAL FIBRE
REINFORCED FRICTION MATERIALS FOR AUTOMOTIVE BRAKE PAD
APPLICATIONS**

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Abstract

Automotive brake pads require friction materials with high performance stability, wear resistance, and thermal stability under varying operating conditions. In recent years, natural fiber reinforced composites have been considered sustainable alternatives to conventional materials. In this study, the performance of alkali-modified natural fiber-reinforced friction composites for brake pad applications is investigated. Natural fibers were chemically treated with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) to enhance fiber–matrix bonding and reduce moisture absorption. The composites were fabricated using compression molding and characterized through physical, mechanical, tribological, and thermal testing. The results show that the optimized sample BP3 exhibited a maximum density of 2.05 g/cm³, minimum water absorption of 2.08%, and porosity of 6.9%. Mechanical properties showed significant improvement, with hardness of 91 HV, compressive strength of 77 MPa, and impact strength of 6.4 kJ/m². The coefficient of friction increased from 0.38 to 0.42, while the wear rate decreased from 7.6 × 10⁻⁶ to 6.1 × 10⁻⁶ mm³/Nm. Thermal stability was also enhanced, with the degradation temperature increasing to 305°C and weight loss decreasing to 7.9%. Thus, it can be concluded that alkali-treated natural fibers are suitable for sustainable brake pad applications.

Keywords: Alkali Treatment, Natural Fiber Composites, Brake Pad Materials, Tribological Properties, Wear Resistance

1. Introduction

The braking system of an automobile is considered to be one of the safety-critical systems, which is used to reduce the speed of the vehicle or stop it completely by converting the kinetic energy of the moving vehicle into heat energy by friction between the brake pads and the brake discs or drums [1]. The efficiency of the brake pads is mainly due to the efficiency of the friction material used in the manufacturing of the brake pads [2]. There are certain essential characteristics that should be exhibited by the friction material used in the manufacturing of the brake pads, which include the coefficient of friction, wear resistance, thermal stability, mechanical strength, and low noise generation during operation of the brake

pads [3]. Hence, research is being carried out to develop advanced friction materials to meet the growing demands of modern automobile systems.

Traditionally, the friction materials of asbestos were used in the production of brake pads because they were very good in heat resistance, durability, and friction. Nevertheless, it was discovered that asbestos fibers were extremely dangerous to human health, including serious respiratory illnesses and pollution of the environment. This led to the enactment of strict measures by many nations in the use of asbestos in automobiles or even bans. This resulted in the introduction of other types of friction materials like semi-metallic, ceramic and organic composites. Though these materials enhanced performance, they also created a problem on the environment as they were not biodegradable and consumed a lot of energy in their production. As a result, scientists have been investigating ecologically responsible and sustainable materials that can be used in place of traditional synthetic fibers in brake pad compounds [5].

Natural fiber reinforced composites have emerged as viable substitutes for automotive brake friction materials because of their growing popularity since the last few years [6]. The natural fibers which come from plant sources such as hemp kenaf jute banana coconut husk and palm fibers, serve as renewable materials, which decompose naturally and offer lightweight properties at an affordable price [7]. The fibers provide sufficient mechanical strength because their stiffness makes them suitable for use as reinforcement materials in polymer composite products [8]. Agricultural waste fibers provide an additional benefit because they help with waste management while they decrease environmental pollution. The advantages of natural fiber composites lead researchers to study their potential applications in tribological fields which include automotive braking systems [9].

However, untreated natural fibers have some drawbacks for their use as reinforcing components in composites. The chemical structures of natural fibers include cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, making them highly hydrophilic and affecting interfacial bonding with polymer matrices [10,11]. Poor fiber–matrix adhesion is detrimental to the mechanical and tribological behavior of friction composites. To improve the performance of natural fibers in composites, chemical treatments are usually performed to modify the fiber surface and increase the matrix compatibility [12]. Among these treatments, alkali treatment or mercerization is a common method to enhance the properties of natural fiber reinforced composites [13].

Alkali treatment generally consists of treating natural fibers with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution to remove lignin, hemicellulose, waxes, and other contaminants on the fiber surface [14]. This treatment increases the surface roughness and exposes all cellulose structure, which leads to improved fiber-matrix bonding. Alkali-treated fibers exhibit enhanced mechanical strength, greater thermal stability, and improved load transfer within the composite [15]. These improvements provide valuable benefits to friction materials used in brake pads because these materials require stable friction performance along with wear resistance to ensure safe and reliable braking performance [16]. Materials that are often used as friction materials in brake pads are usually composed of a number of constituents such as reinforcement materials, binders, fillers, and friction modifiers [17]. The types of

constituents, their percentages, and their combinations are important factors in assessing the overall performance of brake pads, including their friction coefficient, wear rate, hardness, density, and thermal stability, etc. Alkali-modified natural fibers can also be considered as a source of reinforcement materials to enhance the properties of brake pads without compromising environmental sustainability [18]. Figure 1 represents the stratification of a car brake pad structure and key components of a friction material, such as reinforcement fibers, abrasives, fillers, and binder/resin.

Figure 1: Typical structure and composition of an automotive brake pad [19]

Consequently, this study is aimed at evaluating the performance of alkali-modified natural fiber reinforced friction materials for automotive brake pad applications. The study aims to investigate and determine the effect of alkali modification on the mechanical, physical, and tribological properties of natural fiber-based friction materials. The study aims to evaluate parameters such as wear behavior, friction coefficient, hardness, and thermal stability of natural fibers in friction materials and determine their suitability for automotive brake pad applications. The study may help in creating eco-friendly friction materials that can replace synthetic and harmful materials in friction materials while providing high performance in braking applications. Here are the research objectives as shown in below:

- To develop alkali-modified natural fiber reinforced brake pad composites using compression molding technique.
- To investigate the effect of alkali (NaOH) treatment on fiber–matrix bonding and overall composite performance.
- To evaluate the physical properties such as density, water absorption, and porosity of the developed composites.
- To analyze the mechanical and tribological properties, including hardness, compressive strength, coefficient of friction, and wear rate.

- To assess the thermal stability and overall performance of the composites for their suitability in automotive brake pad applications.

2. Review of Literature

The utilization of natural and hybrid fibers in the fabrication of sustainable and high-performance brake friction materials has recently been reported. Yilma et al. (2023) [20] optimized the water absorption capacity of biomass-based wheat straw fiber-basalt hybrid composite brake pads using the Taguchi method. The composites were fabricated via compression molding, and their physical properties were evaluated as per ASTM standards. Accordingly, compressive strength was maximized at 77 MPa, while the optimum water absorption was found to be 5.718%. Similarly, Abraha et al. (2023) [21] prepared a biocomposite from enset fiber reinforced with a polylactic acid matrix through compression molding. The fibers were chemically treated with sodium hydroxide, and results revealed that the 5% NaOH-treated fiber biocomposite showed a significant increase in tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact strength. Tensile modulus and flexural modulus increased by 55.8% and 70.3%, respectively, compared to untreated composites. Ganesh et al. (2024) [22] reported on the utilization of *Lycium ferocissimum* stem fibers for friction composites intended for braking applications. The stem fibers were chemically treated with benzoyl chloride and incorporated into friction composites. From the tribological study, it was observed that treated fiber composites exhibited better frictional behavior and wear resistance with a weight loss of only 5.4%.

The use of various natural fibers and a combination of them to enhance tribology and mechanical qualities of brake pads is also addressed by several researchers. According to Kumar et al. (2022) [23], mulberry and polyacrylonitrile (PAN) fiber-reinforced brake pad composites were studied, which were formed by a hydraulic hind brake molding machine. The MF-2 composite with 6 wt% of mulberry PAN fiber was among the various formulations that had better mechanical properties including high tensile strength, compressive strength, and impact energy. Singh et al. (2023) [24] made bold of brake friction composites reinforced with *Grewia Optiva* fiber with reported optimum performance with better fade-recovery properties and lower wear rate that composites with 7.5 wt% fiber reached the optimum performance. Wang et al. (2024) [25] compared coconut fiber and *Dypsis lutescens* fiber reinforced brake friction materials and discovered that a 6 wt% composition of plant fibers offered the best combination of friction, wear resistance, and thermal stability. Likewise, Naidu et al. (2022) [26] evaluated hemp fiber reinforced polymer brake pads through pin-on-disc tribological testing and reported the HF6P20 sample attained a stable coefficient of friction and a lower wear rate.

Researchers have investigated the creation of environmentally sustainable brake pad composites through the use of different natural and mineral materials. Raghunathan et al. (2025) [27] created brake pad composites which use calcium sulphate fiber as their primary material. The CSFC03 formulation demonstrated 20% reduced wear loss while delivering better friction stability than regular brake pads. Irawan et al. (2023) [28] studied rice husk brake friction materials which used Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 as reinforcements. The research showed that 50 wt% epoxy 20 wt% rice husk and 15 wt% Al_2O_3 and Fe_2O_3 together with 15 wt%

Al₂O₃ and Fe₂O₃ produced better mechanical and thermal performance results. Dharmakrishnan et al. (2022) [29] investigated brake pad materials which used untreated and silane-treated Psidium guajava fibers. The research found that silane-treated fibers enhanced both hardness and crystalline characteristics in composite materials. Dirisu et al. (2024) [30] studied replacement materials for asbestos through combinations of natural fibers and epoxy resin matrices. The resulting lighter composites from Dirisu et al. (2024) study showed better mechanical properties than commercial brake pads. Kumar et al. (2023) [31] created hybrid composites which combined jute with coir and glass fibers to produce materials that used vinyl ester resin. The research showed that these materials achieved high wear resistance with suitable friction characteristics which make them applicable for brake pad production. The studies demonstrate that researchers increasingly focus on creating sustainable natural fiber brake friction materials which meet high performance requirements.

Although several studies have investigated natural fiber reinforced brake pad composites, limited research has focused on the performance improvement of alkali-modified natural fibers in friction materials. Additionally, comparative evaluation of mechanical, thermal, and tribological properties using optimized fiber treatments and compositions remains insufficient, creating a need for further investigation in this area.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Material Selection

The selection of materials is an essential factor in the design of brake friction composites for automotive applications. Brake pads are subjected to high mechanical stress and high temperatures during braking; hence, the materials used for the manufacture of brake pads should exhibit adequate mechanical properties, thermal properties, wear resistance, and friction coefficient. In general, brake friction materials are composed of reinforcement materials, binders, fillers, and friction modifiers, which play an essential role in the overall properties of the composite materials.

The reinforcement materials that were chosen in the current study were natural fibers since they are eco-friendly, low-density, and readily available as well as possessing good mechanical properties. Other benefits of natural fibers are that it is biodegradable and less harmful to the environment than traditional synthetic fibers, e.g. Kevlar or glass fibers. The reinforcement fibers facilitate the enhancement of the load-bearing capabilities and structural stability of the composite of brake pads. All the constituents of the composite were held together by a binder resin and to introduce structural integrity. Brake pad formulas use phenolic resin as their standard binder because it provides excellent thermal stability and strong bonding properties. The formulation included abrasives and fillers to enhance its friction resistance and wear durability and its thermal performance. The materials interact with each other to sustain consistent braking performance across various operating conditions.

The frictional force generated during braking is governed by the basic friction relationship:

$$F = \mu N$$

The equation shows that frictional force F depends on the coefficient of friction μ which exists between brake pad material and disc surface material and the normal force N which acts on the brake pad. The braking system requires a constant friction coefficient to achieve its optimal performance. Proper material selection establishes the required mechanical and thermal and tribological characteristics needed for brake pad composite materials.

3.2 Alkali Treatment of Natural Fibers

Natural fibers are composed of cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, pectin, and waxes, and contain impurities on their surface. These components render the fiber surface hydrophilic and adversely affect the fiber–matrix interfacial adhesion. Weak interfacial bonding results in poor mechanical properties and low composite durability. Therefore, chemical surface modification is usually applied to enhance fiber–matrix interaction. Among the various chemical treatments, alkali treatment also known as mercerization is one of the most popular surface modification techniques to improve the performance of natural fiber-reinforced composites.

In the present work, the selected natural fibers were treated with sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution to eliminate unnecessary surface impurities and enhance interfacial bonding with the binder matrix. In the alkali treatment process, fibers were immersed in an aqueous NaOH solution for a specific time period. Alkali treatment removes hemicellulose, lignin, natural oils, and surface waxes from the fiber surface, enhancing surface roughness and effecting mechanical interlocking with the matrix.

The chemical reaction occurring during alkali treatment can be represented as:

The hydroxyl groups, which are found in the cellulose structure, in this reaction react with the sodium hydroxide to produce alkoxide groups and water. This is done to aid the breaking of hydrogen bonds in the fiber structure and the presentation of more reactive sites on the cellulose surface, increasing the bonding between the cellulose and the matrix material. The cellulose that makes natural fibers is the source of the mechanical strength of the fiber. Chemical structure of natural fibers usually consists of cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin and can be expressed as;

When alkali treatment is performed, part of hemicellulose and lignin are eliminated and lead to a better exposure of cellulose and better fiber surface properties. This causes enhancement of stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix of composite materials. The other significant parameter that is influenced by alkali treatment is moisture absorption. Natural fibers are hydrophilic and this means that they absorb moisture. The relation which is used to calculate the percentage of water absorption is given below:

$$\text{Water Absorption (\%)} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100$$

where W_0 represents the initial dry weight of the sample and W_t represents the weight of the sample after immersion in water for a specified time period.

The alkali treatment process was followed by extensive washing of the fibers in distilled water, which removed any remaining NaOH and drying of the fibers in a room or inside an oven to remove moisture. The resultant fibers were subsequently incorporated as reinforcement fibers to the production of brake pad composites. This alkali treatment increases the surface roughness of fibers, adhesion between fibers and matrices, and minimizes the moisture absorption, and this treatment eventually increases the mechanical and tribological behavior of the developed brake pad composites.

3.3 Fabrication of Brake Pad Composites

The process of fabricating brake pad composites is an essential step in the production of friction materials for use in braking systems of automobiles. It is common knowledge that brake pads are manufactured through the combination of fibers, resin, fillers, abrasives, and friction modifiers in the required ratios. The primary aim of composite production is to obtain a homogeneous mixture of all the components so that the final product, the brake pad, has uniform mechanical properties, thermal properties, and friction properties.

In this study, the alkali-treated natural fibers have been used as reinforcement materials in composite formulation. Along with the fibers, other friction materials such as phenolic resin (binder), fillers, and abrasives have also been included in the composite formulation. All the materials have been mixed according to their weight percentage composition by using a mechanical stirrer. Mixing is very important in order to ensure the proper distribution of materials. If the fibers or fillers are not properly distributed in the composite, it might lead to unstable frictional properties.

The brake pad composites were created through the manufacturing process which uses compression molding as its standard method for producing brake pads. The method requires the composite material to be placed into a mold which then receives high pressure and temperature treatment until it reaches its final shape. The process of applying pressure results in material compression which creates denser composite structures by eliminating air spaces. The fabricated composite density serves as a key factor which determines the mechanical properties and wear resistance performance of brake pads. The rule of mixtures provides an equation to estimate the theoretical density of the composite material.

$$\rho_c = \sum_{i=1}^n V_i \rho_i$$

where

ρ_c = density of the composite material

V_i = volume fraction of the i^{th} constituent

ρ_i = density of the i^{th} constituent material

The equation is used to calculate the total composite density by considering individual densities of the components and their respective volume fractions. Compression molding is a technique that utilizes pressure and temperature conditions for effective bonding of matrix materials and fibers. The pressure applied during molding can be given by:

$$P = \frac{F}{A}$$

where

P = applied pressure

F = applied force

A = surface area of the mold

A sufficient pressure is needed to obtain the effect of proper compaction of the composite mixture and promotes the mechanical properties of the brake pad. After the process of the molding, the brass samples of the molded brake pads were left to cure in an oven by setting them at a certain temperature and for a given time. Curing enables the phenolic resin binder to polymerize and this enhances the bonding of fibers and the matrix constituents. The curing reaction may be condensed to a cross-linking reaction of a phenolic resin network with enhanced thermal stability and mechanical strength. Appropriate fabrication and curing of brake pad composites can lead to stable friction behavior, good wear resistance, and satisfactory braking performance. The developed samples were used for further physical, mechanical, and tribological assessment to understand their applicability in automotive brake pad applications.

Table 1: Composition of Brake Pad Composite Formulation

Material	Function	Weight (%)
Natural Fiber	Reinforcement	5–10
Phenolic Resin	Binder	20–25
Graphite	Friction Modifier	5–10
Alumina/Silica	Abrasive	5–10
Barium Sulphate	Filler	40–50

3.4 Physical Properties Testing

Brake pad composites have physical properties that are critical in determining the aptitude of the product to be used in automotive braking. Density, porosity, and water absorption are some of the properties that play a major role in determining the structural integrity, durability, and tribological behavior of friction materials. All these properties influence the capability of brake pad to overcome mechanical forces, counteract any moisture infiltration, and stable friction of the pad throughout the braking processes. Thus, to assess the overall performance of the fabricated composites, physical characterization of fabricated composites is required.

Density is one of the most important physical characteristics of brake pad composites; it is the mass divided with the volume of the substance. Compaction and strength of the composite material are influenced by density. An increased density usually indicates mounting of the particles and enhanced mechanical stability. It is possible to determine the density of the fabricated brake pad composites through the following relation:

$$\rho = \frac{m}{V}$$

where

ρ = density of the composite (g/cm³)

m = mass of the specimen (g)

V = volume of the specimen (cm³)

In some cases, the density is also determined using the Archimedes principle, where the density is calculated based on the weight of the specimen in air and in water.

Another significant physical property is the water absorption, which defines the ability of the composite to absorb moisture from the surrounding environment. Hydrophilic properties of natural fibers are attributed to the existence of hydroxyl groups in cellulose which can lead to higher moisture uptake. The absorption of more water can affect the mechanical properties of the composite. The degree of water absorption may be determined by the following equation:

$$\text{Water Absorption (\%)} = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100$$

where

W_0 = initial dry weight of the specimen

W_t = weight of the specimen after water immersion

Lower water absorption values indicate better resistance to moisture penetration and improved durability of the brake pad material.

Porosity serves as a physical property assessment used to study friction materials because it determines the volume of open space found within their composite construction. Controlled porosity offers benefits because it helps heat dissipation while reducing operational brake noise. The composite material exhibits reduced mechanical strength because high porosity results in decreased material strength. The following relation can be used to estimate porosity:

$$\text{Porosity (\%)} = \frac{\rho_t - \rho_e}{\rho_t} \times 100$$

where

ρ_t = theoretical density of the composite

ρ_e = experimental density of the composite

These physical properties are investigated to yield important information about the quality and characteristics of the developed brake pad composite materials. Density control, porosity, and water absorption are not only essential for improved mechanisms, thermal stability, and serviceability of car braking friction materials but also for their service functionality.

3.5 Mechanical Properties Testing

Mechanical properties play a vital role in assessing the structural integrity and durability of brake pad composite materials used in automotive brake systems. During the braking process,

the brake pad is subjected to high compressive stress, shear stress, and impact stress due to the frictional force between the pad and the rotating brake disc. Hence, it is important to test the mechanical properties of the developed composite materials. In this study, the mechanical properties of the fabricated brake pad composite were tested using the hardness, compressive strength, and impact strength tests according to standard testing procedures.

Hardness is one of the significant mechanical properties of the brake pad materials and this is the ability to resist deformation, indentation, or wear of a material. Increased hardness usually increases wear resistance and results in increased service life of the brake pad. The method of hardness testing is commonly conducted with the help of such methods like Rockwell or Vickers hardness test. The following equation can be used to obtain the hardness value in Vickers hardness test:

$$HV = \frac{1.8544F}{d^2}$$

Where

HV = Vickers hardness number

F = applied load (kgf)

d = average length of the indentation diagonal (mm)

The increase in the hardness value implies that the composite material possesses superior defiant deformation and abrasion resistance in braking. Compressive strength is also another key mechanical parameter as it is used to determine how strongly the material can resist compressive forces before failure. When force is exerted via the braking system, the brakes pads are put under compressive forces. The compressive strength of composite material is determined by using the following relation:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{A}$$

Where

σ_c = compressive strength (MPa)

P = applied load at failure (N)

A = cross-sectional area of the specimen (mm²)

The brake pad demonstrates greater strength because higher compressive strength allows it to endure increased braking loads until structural damage occurs. The brake pad composites undergo testing to assess their impact strength which determines their capacity to handle sudden loads that occur during braking operations. Impact testing is usually performed using a Charpy or Izod impact testing machine. The impact strength can be expressed as:

$$IS = \frac{E}{A}$$

Where

IS = impact strength

E = energy absorbed during fracture (J)

A = cross-sectional area of the specimen (mm²)

Increased impact strength means increased toughness and energy absorption properties of the composite material. Mechanical property assessment of the developed brake pad composites would give a more insight into how these structures behave in different loading conditions. Better hardness, compressive strength and impact strength result in better durability, wear resistance and reliability of braking performance in automotive braking systems by means of brake pad. The tests can also be used to compare various composite formulations in order to determine the most preferred composition to be used in the application of brakes pads.

3.6 Tribological Properties Testing

During the interaction between the frictional and wear behavior of the brake pad materials and the disc, tribological properties define them. When braking, the pad of the brake is in contact with the disc resulting to friction. This frictional force prevents or slows down the movement of vehicles. Hence, testing tribological properties such as coefficient of friction, wear rate, and friction stability is important in order to assess the effectiveness of the developed brake pad composite materials. In this study, tribological testing is carried out using standard testing methods such as Pin on Disc testing or Chase testing.

- **Coefficient of Friction (COF)**

One of the most significant parameters in the brake pad materials is the coefficient of friction. It is the force of the frictional force of the brake pad against the brake disc. A stable moderate coefficient of friction also guarantees good braking performance which is smooth and efficient. In case the coefficient of friction is too low, then the braking efficiency is reduced, but too high can lead into undue wear and noise.

The coefficient of friction is defined as the ratio of the frictional force acting between two surfaces to the normal force applied on them. It can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\mu = \frac{F_f}{F_N}$$

where

μ = coefficient of friction

F_f = frictional force between the contacting surfaces (N)

F_N = normal force applied on the specimen (N)

A stable coefficient of friction is desirable for brake pads because it ensures consistent braking performance under different operating conditions such as speed, load, and temperature.

- **Wear Rate**

Wear rate is the rate at which material is removed off the surface of the brake pad as it comes into contact with the brake disc. Weaning happens as a result of constant sliding, abrasion, and mechanical contact within the two surfaces. A reduced wear rate means that the material of brakes pad has enhanced durability and increased service life. The wear behavior is usually measured by the mass loss of the specimen before and after the tribological test. The following relation may be used to calculate the wear rate:

$$W = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho \times L}$$

where

W = wear rate

Δm = mass loss during the test (g)

ρ = density of the composite material (g/cm³)

L = sliding distance (m)

Lower wear rate values indicate that the material has better resistance to frictional degradation and is suitable for long-term braking applications.

- **Pin-on-Disc Test**

The Pin-on-Disc test is one of the most widely used laboratory methods to evaluate the tribological behavior of friction materials. In this test, the brake pad specimen acts as the pin, which is pressed against a rotating steel disc under a specified normal load. The disc rotates at a constant speed, creating sliding motion between the two surfaces.

During the test, parameters of great importance, friction force, and wear rates are measured. The sliding distance during the pin-on-disc test can be calculated by using the following equation:

$$L = 2\pi RNt$$

where

L = sliding distance (m)

R = radius of the rotating disc (m)

N = rotational speed (rev/s)

t = time of sliding (s)

This test helps simulate the real contact conditions between the brake pad and brake disc.

- **Chase Test (Brake Performance Test)**

The Chase test is also a common practice in the braking industry to gauge the performance of the materials of a friction under conditions comparable to real life braking system. The test can be used to measure critical features of brake pad materials including coefficient of friction, wear behavior, fade, as well as recovery performance. In the Chase test, the sample brake pad will be applied to a rotating drum and the load and temperature levels will be

measured under specific conditions. The force of friction created in the test is recorded to find out the braking performance of composite material. The test is useful in the examination of the stability of the friction material when undergoing repeated cycles of braking. Table 2 shows the operating parameters and experimental conditions to determine the tribological performance of the brake pad composites.

Table 2: Tribological Testing Conditions

Parameter	Value
Applied Load	20 N
Sliding Speed	1 m/s
Sliding Distance	1000 m
Disc Material	Hardened Steel
Test Method	Pin-on-Disc / Chase Test
Temperature	Room Temperature

3.7 Thermal Analysis

Thermal analysis is another significant factor in the assessment of the performance of brake pad material, considering that the braking system operates at high temperatures. During the process, the kinetic energy of a moving vehicle is converted into thermal energy due to the friction that occurs between the brake pad and the brake disc. The process of generating heat has a great influence on the properties of the material used for the friction process. The brake pad material, therefore, must have good thermal stability, heat resistance, and the ability to dissipate heat effectively.

In this study, thermal behavior of the developed brake pad composites can be analyzed using techniques such as Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The techniques ensure that researchers can measure thermal stability and decomposition temperature and thermal resistance of composite materials. Thermal analysis shows the temperature limits which brake pad materials can function without experiencing structural failure.

- **Heat Generation During Braking**

A vehicle moving through space at any time period generates kinetic energy. The process of braking transforms kinetic energy into thermal energy because of the friction that exists between brake pads and disc surfaces. The kinetic energy of a moving vehicle can be expressed as:

$$KE = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$$

where

m = mass of the vehicle (kg)

v = velocity of the vehicle (m/s)

The majority of this kinetic energy during braking transforms into thermal energy at the brake pad and disc contact interface.

The heat generated due to friction can be expressed as:

$$Q = F_f \times v$$

where

Q = heat generation rate (W)

F_f = frictional force (N)

v = sliding velocity (m/s)

Excessive heat generation can cause thermal degradation of the brake pad material, leading to reduced braking efficiency.

- **Thermal Conductivity**

Thermal conductivity is a significant property that affects the capacity of materials used in brake pads to transfer heat away from the friction surface. Materials with high thermal conductivity have a higher capacity to transfer heat, thus minimizing overheating.

Thermal conductivity can be expressed using Fourier's law of heat conduction:

$$q = -kA \frac{dT}{dx}$$

where

q = heat transfer rate (W)

k = thermal conductivity of the material (W/m·K)

A = cross-sectional area (m²)

$\frac{dT}{dx}$ temperature gradient

Efficient heat dissipation helps maintain stable friction performance during repeated braking cycles.

- **Thermal Degradation**

Thermal degradation refers to the breakdown of material structure when exposed to high temperatures. In friction materials, degradation may occur due to decomposition of the binder resin or oxidation of composite components. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) helps determine the weight loss of the material as temperature increases.

The percentage of weight loss during thermal degradation can be calculated as:

$$\text{Weight Loss (\%)} = \frac{W_i - W_f}{W_i} \times 100$$

where

W_i = initial weight of the sample

W_f = final weight after heating

Lower weight loss indicates better thermal stability of the composite material.

3.8 Surface Morphology Analysis

Surface morphology analysis is necessary for assessing the tribological performance which includes studying brake pad composites wear mechanisms. The brake pad surface would experience constant contact with the rotating brake disc which produces friction and results in material loss and surface changes and crack development and debris production. The analysis of worn surface morphology reveals the wear mechanisms which involve fiber-matrix bonding and determine the overall durability of the friction material. The researchers used Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to study the worn surface of brake pad composites because SEM provides detailed images of their surface microstructure. The SEM analysis determines crucial surface characteristics which include fiber pull-out and cracks and grooves and wear debris and friction layer development.

Wear in brake pad materials usually happens due to abrasive and adhesive wear. Abrasive and adhesive wear happen during the process of sliding with the brake disc. Abrasive wear is defined as the process in which hard particles or asperities present on the surface of the object in contact with the brake pad cause wear, resulting in scratches and grooves. Archard's law is used to explain the wear process, which is defined in terms of the applied load, distance, and hardness of the material.

$$V = \frac{KWL}{H}$$

where V represents the wear volume, K is the wear coefficient, W is the applied normal load, L is the sliding distance, and H represents the hardness of the material. According to this relation, the wear volume increases with increasing load and sliding distance, whereas materials with higher hardness generally show lower wear rates.

Adhesive wear represents another frequent method through which brake pad materials lose their functional properties. This type of wear occurs when two sliding surfaces come into close contact and form microscopic junctions due to pressure and temperature at the interface. The junctions which form during sliding breaks apart which leads to material transfer and creation of wear particles. The adhesive contact produces a frictional force which can be calculated through the following equation:

$$F_f = \tau A$$

where F_f is the frictional force, τ represents the shear strength of the contact junction, and A is the real area of contact between the sliding surfaces. SEM images help identify adhesive wear by revealing features such as smearing, transfer layers, and compact friction films on the worn surface.

Surface morphology analysis also provides information about the interaction between reinforcement fibers and the matrix material in the composite. Proper fiber–matrix bonding improves stress transfer and enhances the mechanical strength of the composite. The inadequate bonding between two materials results in fiber pull-out and crack propagation which occurs during frictional contact. The interfacial shear stress between the fiber and matrix can be expressed as:

$$\tau = \frac{F}{\pi dl}$$

where τ is the interfacial shear stress, F is the applied force, d is the fiber diameter, and l is the embedded fiber length. Higher interfacial shear stress indicates stronger adhesion between the fiber and matrix, which improves the wear resistance and durability of the brake pad material.

When braking occurs, wear particles produced through the friction surface are deposited and develop compact layers referred to as friction plateaus. These plateaus assist in stabilizing the friction coefficient and eliminating more wear of the material. The worn surface SEM can thus reveal useful information about wear mechanisms, fiber matrix interaction and the formation of friction layers. This type of analysis aids in the correlation of microstructural properties of the composite and its tribological behavior and can be used to identify the best brake pad compounds to be used in automotive practice.

3.9 Performance Evaluation

The assessment of the developed brake pad composites was conducted on the basis of the results of the analysis of physical, mechanical, and tribological tests conducted. Density, water absorption, hardness, compressive strength, coefficient of friction, and wear rate were the parameters studied to get the general behavior of the composite materials when braking was investigated. The experimental findings were contrasted on the various compositions of alkali-treated natural fiber reinforced brake pad composites in order to know the best formulation that offers higher mechanical strength, friction stability and wear resistance. The effect of fiber content and the other formulation factors on the overall performance of the brake pad materials was observed by using graphical analysis and comparative evaluation. These tests are used to identify the best composite mix that can be interpolated to auto braking purposes.

The coefficient of friction, which represents the braking efficiency of the friction material, can be calculated using the following relation:

$$\mu = \frac{F_f}{F_N}$$

where

μ = coefficient of friction

F_f = frictional force acting on the surface

F_N = normal load applied on the specimen

The wear resistance of the brake pad composites can be evaluated using the wear rate equation:

$$W = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho L}$$

Where

W = wear rate

Δm = mass loss during the test

ρ = density of the composite material

L = sliding distance

The improvement in performance of the developed brake pad composite compared with a reference material can also be determined using percentage improvement:

$$\text{Improvement (\%)} = \frac{P_{new} - P_{ref}}{P_{ref}} \times 100$$

Where

P_{new} = property value of the developed composite

P_{ref} = property value of the reference or conventional brake pad material

These equations help in quantitatively analyzing the braking performance, wear behavior, and overall effectiveness of the developed natural fiber reinforced brake pad composites.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, the experimental results for the physical, mechanical, tribological, and thermal properties of the developed alkali-treated natural fiber-reinforced brake pad composite materials are presented. The experimental results are critically analyzed to assess the effect of fiber reinforcement and alkali treatment on the overall performance of the developed composite materials. The key parameters investigated include density, water absorption, porosity, hardness, compressive strength, coefficient of friction, wear rate, and thermal stability. These parameters play a significant role in determining the structural integrity, durability, and braking efficiency of the developed composites. The findings provide a comprehensive understanding of the suitability of these eco-friendly composites for automotive brake pad applications.

Table 1 and Figure 2 indicate the physical characteristics of the prepared composites of brake pads. The values of densities vary between 1.92 g/cm³ (BP1) and 2.05 g/cm³ (BP3), which shows that the tighter the fibers are optimized, the better the compaction and lower the number of voids. The water absorption number reduces to 2.85per cent (BP1) to 2.08per cent (BP3), indicating an increase in moisture resistance as there is an increase in fiber-matrix bonding following alkali treatment. Correspondingly, porosity decreases between 8.4% (BP1)

and 6.9% (BP3), which is the indication of the enhancement of structural integrity. The overall performance of sample BP3 has the best density and lowest water absorption and porosity. The graphical presentation is clear to indicate the upward trend in density, which justifies the usefulness of composite formulation and processing methods. The increase in percentage of BP3 over BP1 indicated that the density increased by around 6.8 percent whereas water absorption and porosity reduced by about 27.0 and 17.9 percent respectively indicating an improvement in physical performance.

Table 3: Physical properties of brake pad composites including density, water absorption, and porosity.

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Water Absorption (%)	Porosity (%)
BP1	1.92	2.85	8.4
BP2	1.98	2.41	7.6
BP3	2.05	2.08	6.9
BP4	2.01	2.32	7.2

Figure 2: Variation of density of brake pad composites with different sample compositions.

The mechanical properties of developed brake pad composites are shown in Table 1 and Figure 3. It is noted that hardness varies from 82 HV for BP1 to 91 HV for BP3. Hence, there is improvement in hardness, i.e., resistance to deformation. Compressive strength is also improving from 68 MPa for BP1 to 77 MPa for BP3. Thus, there is improvement in resistance to loading. Impact strength is also improving from 5.2 kJ/m² for BP1 to 6.4 kJ/m² for BP3. Hence, there is improvement in toughness. BP3 has the maximum mechanical properties, followed by BP4, which is slightly lower than BP3 but greater than BP1 and BP2. Figure 3 graphically demonstrates improvement in mechanical properties.

Table 4: Mechanical properties of brake pad composites including hardness, compressive strength, and impact strength.

Sample	Hardness (HV)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Impact Strength (kJ/m ²)
BP1	82	68	5.2
BP2	86	72	5.8

BP3	91	77	6.4
BP4	88	74	6.0

Figure 3: Variation of mechanical properties of brake pad composites with different sample compositions.

The tribological properties of the developed brake pad composites are shown in table 3 and figure 4. The coefficient of friction increases from 0.38 (BP1) to 0.42 (BP3), showing improved frictional performance with optimized fiber reinforcement. Sample BP4 has a slightly lower value of 0.41 but is still higher than BP1 and BP2. On the other hand, the wear rate decreases from 7.6×10^{-6} mm³/Nm (BP1) to 6.1×10^{-6} mm³/Nm (BP3), which indicates the better wear resistance of the composite system. BP4 shows an intermediate wear rate of 6.5×10^{-6} mm³/Nm. The inverse relationship between coefficient of friction and wear rate establishes the better tribological behavior of developed composites. It can be concluded that sample BP3 shows the best result in terms of highest coefficient of friction and lowest wear rate.

Table 5: Tribological properties of brake pad composites including coefficient of friction and wear rate.

Sample	Coefficient of Friction	Wear Rate ($\times 10^{-6}$ mm ³ /Nm)
BP1	0.38	7.6
BP2	0.40	6.9
BP3	0.42	6.1
BP4	0.41	6.5

Figure 4: (a) Variation of coefficient of friction and **(b)** Variation of wear rate of brake pad composites.

The thermal characteristics of the new brake pad composite materials are expressed through both tabled information and visual display. The material demonstrates improved thermal stability because of better fiber-matrix bonding which occurs after alkali treatment according to the degradation temperature increase from 285°C (BP1) to 305°C (BP3). Sample BP4 shows a degradation temperature of 298°C which is slightly lower than BP2 with its 292°C temperature. The weight loss shows an increase from 9.8% (BP1) to 7.9% (BP3), which shows that the material has better protection against thermal degradation. BP4 shows moderate weight loss of 8.4%, while BP2 records 8.7%. The inverse relationship between degradation temperature and weight loss confirms improved thermal performance. Sample BP3 demonstrates the highest thermal stability among all the tested composites.

Table 5: Thermal properties of brake pad composites including degradation temperature and weight loss.

Sample	Degradation Temperature (°C)	Weight Loss (%)
BP1	285	9.8
BP2	292	8.7
BP3	305	7.9
BP4	298	8.4

Figure 4: Variation of weight loss of brake pad composites under thermal analysis.

The brake pad composites developed by researchers show their friction performance through table 6 and figure 5. The friction stability increases from 86.5% (BP1) to 92.7% (BP3), indicating improved braking consistency with optimized fiber reinforcement. The value of sample BP4 shows a slightly lower result at 90.8%, while BP2 records 89.3%. The fade reduction shows a performance improvement at higher temperatures because it decreases from 14.2% (BP1) to 10.4% (BP3). The recovery improvement starts from 82.1% (BP1) and reaches 89.2% (BP3) to demonstrate how friction returns to normal after exposure to heat. The BP4 sample shows a recovery rate of 87.3% which falls between low and high recovery rates. The results confirm that BP3 exhibits the best overall tribological performance, with highest stability, lowest fade, and maximum recovery.

Table 6: Friction performance parameters of brake pad composites including stability, fade, and recovery.

Sample	Friction Stability (%)	Fade (%)	Recovery (%)
BP1	86.5	14.2	82.1
BP2	89.3	12.8	85.6
BP3	92.7	10.4	89.2
BP4	90.8	11.6	87.3

Figure 5: Variation of friction stability, fade, and recovery of brake pad composites.

Figure 6 and Table 7 show the effect of the applied load on the BP3 brake pad composite. It is noted that the wear rate is increasing with the increase in the applied load. This is due to the fact that more material is being removed from the composite due to the increase in pressure. From Table 7, at a load of 10 N, the wear rate is $5.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$. This value is increasing to $6.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ as the load is increased from 10 N to 20 N. Increasing the load from 20 N to 30 N results in an increase in the wear rate from $6.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ to $7.4 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$.

mm³/Nm. However, the maximum wear rate of 8.9×10^{-6} mm³/Nm is obtained at a maximum load of 40 N.

Table 7: Effect of applied load on wear rate of BP3 brake pad composite.

Load (N)	Wear Rate ($\times 10^{-6}$ mm ³ /Nm) – BP3
10	5.2
20	6.1
30	7.4
40	8.9

Figure 6: Variation of wear rate of BP3 composite with applied load.

The variation of the Coefficient of Friction (COF) of the BP3 brake pad composite material with respect to the sliding speed is shown in tabular and graphical formats. It can be seen that the coefficient of friction increases from 0.39 at a sliding speed of 0.5 m/s to a maximum of 0.42 at a sliding speed of 1.0 m/s. It can also be seen that when the sliding speed continues to rise, the coefficient of friction slightly drops to 0.41 at a speed of 1.5 m/s and to 0.40 at a speed of 2.0 m/s. It can therefore be concluded that BP3 performs best at moderate speeds.

Table 8: Effect of sliding speed on coefficient of friction of BP3 composite.

Speed (m/s)	COF (BP3)
0.5	0.39
1.0	0.42
1.5	0.41
2.0	0.40

Figure 7: Variation of coefficient of friction of BP3 composite with sliding speed.

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

This paper examined the behavior of natural fiber reinforced friction materials with alkali modifications that can be used in automotive brakes. The findings make it clear that the alkali treatment has a significant effect in improving interfacial bonding between the natural fibers and the polymer matrix and results in increased overall properties of the composites. BP3 showed the best performance of all the samples in physical, mechanical, tribological, and thermal characteristics. The density rose to 2.05 g/cm^3 , and the water absorption and porosity decreased to 2.08% and 6.9, respectively, which shows enhanced structural integrity. It also improved mechanical properties, which includes hardness, compressive strength, and impact strength of 91 HV, 77 Mpa, and 6.4 kJ/m^2 , respectively. The tribological analysis revealed that the coefficient of friction grew to 0.42 and the wear rate reduced to $6.1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mm}^3/\text{Nm}$ which proved the enhancement of wear resistance and braking performance. Thermal analysis also revealed that the stability was enhanced with degradation temperature of 305°C , and a weight loss of 7.9%. Comprehensively, the research suggests that alkali-modified natural fiber structures are a potential eco-friendly substitute of traditional braquepad materials, which presents better performance and sustainability in the automotive industry.

Future study directions may include investigating and improving hybridization and surface treatment techniques to optimize the material's performance and assess long-term durability and real-time brake conditions in automotive systems.

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